

EpiLex0

USER MANUAL

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1. Introduction

1.1. What is EpiLexO

EpiLexO is a web platform dedicated to the creation and editing of lexical resources for ancient fragmentary languages of ancient Italy (such as Oscan, Faliscan, Venetic) which are linked to their testimonies, attestations, and related bibliography. It provides contextual metadata and other information gathered from external links. The web platform is a single-page web application composed of several sections, and each of them provides a set of functionalities that allow for creating and/or editing lexical resources and for interlinking their items with various internal and external datasets.

1.2. The manual

1.2.1. Scope of the manual

This manual is made to be a helpful tool for users in:

- describing the user interface of the web application;
- describing the main functionalities of the application, with easy steps, providing examples, and possible errors that may appear together with possible solutions.

1.2.2. Intended audience

The intended audience of this manual is the typical and potential users of the application, i.e. historical linguists, digital humanists, or epigraphists whose work lies between linguistics and philology for which those languages' testimonies and digitalization are necessary for their studies and research. The manual provides a clear explanation for every single component of the interface and an easy guide (step by step, with examples) for the main functionalities.

1.2.3. How to navigate the manual

Investigating EpiLexO Interface	Investigating EpiLexO Functionalities
<u>Interface description</u> : provides a detailed description of all the components, sections, buttons, and windows. Each section is described in this order: <i>Column A</i> , <i>Column B</i> , <i>Column C</i>	<u>Functionalities of EpiLexO</u> : understanding all the possible and main functionalities of the platform according to the lexicon, inscriptions, and lexical concepts
<u>Icon keys</u> : icons are reported in a list	<u>Troubleshooting</u> : describes the main and recurring issues that a user can encounter while using the platform
	<u>User roles, permissions, and log-in</u> : provides general information about the Log-in and users roles

2. Interface description

The EpiLexO interface is a single-page web application made up of several components organized into 3 sections (or columns); each of them is composed of different panels, providing a set of different functionalities, yet they are all interoperable.

This means that every panel may change according to the item opened or the action performed because they are interlinked and connected.

Fig. 1 - EpiLexO interface

The screenshot displays the EpiLexO interface with three main columns. The left column (Column A) contains three navigation panels: 'Inscriptions', 'Lexicon', and 'Lexical Concept'. The 'Lexicon' panel is active, showing a search bar and a list of entries with red status indicators. The middle column (Column B) is titled 'Epiigraphy' and displays a 'Linker' section with a Latin inscription: 'medikúd túvtikúd niumsiúd dekitúđ míniels . staatiels legú . tanginúđ . aamanafed . esidum . prúfated . úpsed . gaavis . paapiis . gaavieis f'. Below this is an 'Inscription' section with two numbered entries: '1. (edíkkúđ) (úvtíkúđ) (umsiúđ) deŷ(mieis) . s(aatiels) legú . tanginúđ' and '2. aaman(a)fed . eŷt . eđ . úpsed . g(aavis) . paapii(s) . g(aavieis) f(- -)'. A 'Translation' section follows, providing the Italian and English translations of the inscription. The right column (Column C) contains several panels: 'Note Panel', 'Link Panel', 'Bibliography Panel', 'Attestation Panel' (with four entries for 'ItAnt Oscan 3 - úpsed', 'ItAnt Oscan 3 - legú', 'ItAnt Oscan 3 - tanginúđ', and 'ItAnt Oscan 3 - aamanafed'), and 'Metadata Panel' (with 'Edition', 'Epiigraphy', and 'Text' tabs and a table of metadata).

For example, I can open a lexical entry by selecting it from *Column A*. It will be visualized in *Column B*, and its related notes are visualized in *Column C*. Yet if I open a form of that specific lexical entry by selecting it in *Column A*, *Column B* will change to show the form's information, and also notes will be changed accordingly.

2.1. Column A: navigation trees

This section contains the navigation trees for the primary resources: corpus, lexicon, and lexical concepts. In fact, it is divided into 3 main panels:

1. **Inscriptions Panel**
2. **Lexicon Panel**
3. **Lexical Concept Panel**

2.1.1. Inscriptions Panel

Fig. 2 - Inscriptions Panel

This panel shows all the inscriptions files imported on the web application, and therefore available. The texts provide the inscriptions that are precedently annotated and encoded independently from the platform according to the TEI/EpIDoc guidelines, with reference to a specific dialect created specifically for the project. The annotation marks metadata, bibliography, and transcriptions information (e.g. archeological, epigraphic, and linguistic data; bibliographical references, and notes). This panel also includes folders, for the user to organize the inscriptions as needed, and it also includes a search bar. Folders and XML files are not in alphabetical order.

2.1.2. Lexicon Panel

The panel shows the lexical entries in an alphabetical order starting from root entries with an asterisk (prot-italic, proto-Indo-European). It has a search bar and many icons (buttons) used for specific functionalities.

2.1.2.1. Lexicon entry

Fig. 3 - Lexicon Panel

Each entry is introduced by a little arrow ➤ and has a specific format: entry itself, part of speech, @, the label of the language.

On the right, there is a *user icon* 👤 that provides the name of the editor while passing on it with the cursor. Next to it, there is a *status icon* ●, referring to the status of the lexical entry:

- ● red: working → work in progress
- ● yellow: → completed
- ● green: → reviewed

e.g. ➤ COMpreposition@OSC 👤 ●

The example shows the lexical entry for the preposition *com* in Oscan, updated by *test*, status: *working*.

2.1.2.2. Lexicon tree

Fig. 4 - Lexicon Tree

By clicking on the entry, it shows the tree of the lexical entry, organized according to the key ItAnt lexical classes: *Lexical Entry, Form, Sense, and Etymology*, which dynamically correspond to dedicated editing areas in the central part of the interface.

As shown in the example in *Figure 4*, the tree for the entry for the Oscan verb *dedet* has:

- 11 different forms
- 1 sense
- 1 etymology

When the tree is not available, a light blue info message will appear in the top right corner of the web application. The *note icon* shows a note on that particular item, passing on it with the cursor. Notes are entirely visualized and managed on the *Note Panel, Column C*.

2.1.3. Lexical Concept Panel

Fig. 5 - Lexical Concept Panel

This panel shows all the lexical concepts available on the platform in an alphabetical order list. A lexical concept refers to *a mental abstraction, unit of thought, or concept that is lexicalized by a given collection of sense*¹. The classification and list of lexical concepts refer to the semantic fields list of Carl Darling Buck².

¹ In reference to the Ontolex-Lemon Core module, relations *evokes/isEvokedby* or *lexicalizedSense/isLexicalizedSenseOf*

² See the University of Texas' adaptation of semantic fiels: <https://lrc.la.utexas.edu/lex/semantic>

2.2. Column B: main working area

This section is the main working area devoted to editing operations and attestation creation. It is composed of 2 horizontal panels:

1. **Epigraphy Panel** (Text Linker)
2. **Core Panel** (Lexicon Editor)

2.2.1. Epigraphy Panel (Text Linker)

This part is the **Text Linker**, the upper part which is pivotal to the whole platform and it is modular and contextually adaptive according to the text selected from *Column A*.

Fig. 6 - Epigraphy Panel

It shows the actual text in 3 different sections:

1. **Linker**: the text is shown by tokens, which are text elements taken from XML nodes (or manually added in case of empty files). As shown in [Figure 6](#), the text appears by tokens. If a token has a green rectangle, it means that it has attestations. The eye icon means that attestations are present, in fact, they are visualized in *Column C, Attestation Panel*.
2. **Inscription**: shows the transcription of the text converted according to the *Leiden convention*.
3. **Translation**: shows the translation of the text in Italian and English.

The grey top bar of the section shows the title of the Inscription.

2.2.2. Core Panel (Lexicon Editor)

This part is the **Lexicon Editor**, the lower part which is pivotal to the whole platform and it is modular and contextually adaptive according to the lexicon selected from *Column A*.

Fig. 7 - Core Panel

The screenshot shows a web interface for managing lexical entries. At the top, there is a header 'Epigraphy' and a sub-header 'Core'. Below this, a grey bar indicates the entry was 'Lexical Entry CREATED BY imported ON 12/07/2022 12:11:06'. The main form contains several fields: 'Label' with the value 'aasai', 'Etymon' with a toggle switch, 'Uncertain' with an unchecked checkbox, 'Type' with a dropdown menu set to 'word' and a question mark icon, and 'Language' with a dropdown menu set to 'osc'. Below these are three expandable sections: 'MORPHOLOGY' with a 'Part of speech' dropdown set to 'noun' and a question mark icon; 'STEM TYPE' with a text input field containing '-ā'; 'EVOKES' with an empty text input field; and 'COGNATES' with an empty text input field. At the bottom, a grey bar shows 'LAST UPDATE ON 03/05/2023 02:26:12' and a green plus icon.

The panel is opened automatically when selecting a specific lexical entry on *Column A*, and it provides all the general and morphological information about the lexical entry itself:

- **Label:** is the lexical entry itself.
- **Etymon:** a toggle button that can be switched on if the lexical entry is an etymon.
- **Uncertain:** a checkbox that can be checked whenever the lexical entry attestation is uncertain.
- **Type:** a scrolling window referring to the type of lexical entry³.
- **Language:** a scrolling window referring to the language of the lexical entry.
- **Morphology:** provides morphological info of the lexical entry.
- **Stem type:** provides the root or roots of the lexical entry.
- **Evokes:** enables the linking of lexical concepts.
- **Cognates:** enables the linking of cognates of the lexical entry.

The grey top bar of the section shows a sentence that explains when the lexical entry was created, at what time, and by who (*CREATED BY, ON*), and on the far right it also shows the lexical entry status of it with the proper *status icon* ●. While the grey bottom bar of the section reports the last update of the lexical entry (*LAST UPDATE ON*).

e.g. on [Figure 7](#), the *Core Panel* is about the lexical entry `aasai@osc` created by *imported* (it means that it was automatically imported on EpiLexO) on the 12th of July 2022 at 12:11:06, his status is *work in progress* (red *status icon*) and it was last updated on the 3rd of May 2023 at 02:26:12.

³ A reference to the *OntoLex-Lemon model: LexicalEntry, Word, Affix, MultiWordExpression*

The blue *delete icon* on the green box allows one to add a new form, sense, etymology, or bibliography to the specific lexical entry. Once added one of these items, the *Core Panel* will automatically change into a specific panel for each component with specific sections and information (for detailed explanation see further paragraphs).

2.3. Column C: accessory information

This section is dedicated to various kinds of “accessory information” that are either ingested from the input files or added within the interface, given the fact that the content of this column is contextual and dependent on the items selected in sections of *Column A* or *Column B* of the interface. It is divided into 5 different sections:

1. Note Panel
2. Link Panel
3. Bibliography Panel
4. Attestation Panel
5. Metadata Panel

2.3.1. Note Panel

Fig. 8 - Note Panel

The *Note Panel* is contextually dependent, in fact, it shows the notes available according to the item you are visualizing.

For example, if you open the lexical entry from the *Lexicon* in *Column A*, it will show a general note attached to the lexical entry itself, yet if you visualize a sense, the *Note Panel* will change the interface and will show a specific note of the sense only.

2.3.2. Link Panel

Fig. 9 - Link Panel

The *Link Panel* handles the *seeAlso* and *sameAs* properties for referencing other lexical entries (referring to the *Ontolex-lemon* model properties). As shown in [Figure 9](#), it has 2 different boxes used to create internal links with other lexical entries or external links with other resources such as *LiLa*:

1. **See Also:** enables linking lexical entries with similar properties (internal link). when the check box is enabled, it is possible to copy-paste a URI.

2. **Same As:** enables linking with other lexical entries with equal traits from other sources (external link). This particular section has a different interface according to the lexical entry selected. The *delete icon* allows the deletion of the link.

2.3.3. Bibliography Panel

Fig. 10 - Bibliography Panel

The *Bibliography Panel* shows bibliographic references of the lexical entry added in the *Core Panel, Column B* through the *Bibliography window*. The panel shows the list of references, number of references is reported between brackets on the bar, as shown in *Figure 10*. Yet, it is contextually dependent, in fact, it shows the references available according to the item you are visualizing. For example, if you visualize a sense, the *Bibliography Panel* will show the external bibliographic references of the sense only. The *open in a new tab icon* allows the deletion of the bibliographic reference.

2.3.4. Attestation Panel

Fig. 11 - Attestation Panel

The *Attestation Panel* shows all the attestations available for a specific lexical entry, underlined in blue. The *delete icon* opens a new panel referring to that specific attestation.

2.3.5. Metadata Panel

The *Metadata Panel* shows all the metadata for a specific inscription, opened through *Column A*, and shown in *Column B*. This panel is divided into 3 different clicking tabs, and each of them provides extra information:

1. **Edition:** extra info about the current edition of the t6ext uploaded on the platform.
2. **Epigraphy:** extra info about its title, the summary, the place where it was found, the date of origin and discovery, material, info about the institution responsible for conservation, etc.
3. **Text:** extra info as the language, the writing system, division of words, etc.

Fig. 12 - Metadata Panel (Edition)

Note Panel	+
Link Panel	+
Bibliography Panel (2)	+
Attestation Panel	+
Metadata Panel	-

Edition **Epigraphy** Text

EDITION

Title: Inscription ItAnt Oscan 7

Id: 10

Editor: Francesca Murano

Authority: PRIN 2017 "Lingue e culture dell'Italia antica: linguistica storica e modelli digitali | Languages and Cultures of Ancient Italy. Historical Linguistics and Digital Models"

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Fig. 13 - Metadata Panel (Epigraphy)

Note Panel	+
Link Panel	+
Bibliography Panel (2)	+
Attestation Panel	+
Metadata Panel	-

Edition **Epigraphy** Text

EPIGRAPHY

ItAnt ID: ItAnt Oscan 7

Inscription Title: The "Safinim" inscription

Inscription Type: building inscription

Summary: Inscription recording the renovations of the gate and another element of the temple A, and a donation to the sanctuary by a censor, whose name is lost.

Trismegistos ID: [TM 170815](#)

Traditional IDs: [ST Sa 4](#)
[Imit Teruentum 8](#)
[Ve 149](#)

Fig. 14 - Metadata Panel (Text)

Note Panel	+
Link Panel	+
Bibliography Panel (2)	+
Attestation Panel	+
Metadata Panel	-

Edition Epigraphy **Text**

TEXT

Autopsy Author: Francesca Murano

Language: [osc](#)
[osc-Ital-x-oscetr](#)

Ductus: sinistrorse

Word Division Type: punctuation

Writing System: Oscan National alphabet

3. Functionalities of EpiLexO

3.1. Lexicon Functionalities

3.1.1. Add new language

From *Column A, Lexicon Panel*, press the *language icon* which opens the **Language Manager** with a list of languages available in EpiLexO. From here you can manage languages.

Fig. 15 - Language Manager

#	Label	Creator	Description	Entries	Actions
1	osc	<empty>	An extinct language of southern Italy...	105	
2	xfa	VQ	The Faliscan language, the extinct language of the...	1	
3	lat	<empty>	<empty>	57	
4	sbv	middel	sabino...	2	

The Language Manager is organized in a table with 6 columns:

1. **Hashtag**: provides the ordinal number of the list of languages available.
2. **Label**: the language label⁴.
3. **Creator**: the username of the user/editor who added the language.
4. **Description**: the description of the language.
5. **Entries**: number of entries available in that language.
6. **Actions**: provides different buttons for language management: **1.** the *edit icon* opens a window: **Lexical Entries** that provides all the lexical entries related to that particular language.

Fig. 16 - Language Manager. Language Editor

description	<input type="text" value="An extinct language of southern Italy"/>
label	<input type="text" value="osc"/>
lexvo	<input type="text" value="osc"/>

⁴ In reference to the ISO 639 standards by the International Organization for Standardization for the representation of names for languages and language groups.

Fig. 17 - Language Manager. Lexical Entries

Below are the steps to add a new language to the platform from the *Language Manager*. The example shows the addition of English (with label *eng*).

Step 1. Open the *Lexicon Panel* on *Column A*, click on , it will show a window from which you can type the label for a new language (2-3 characters long only). Once typed, click on the green button and the language will be automatically added to the *Language Manager* languages list.

Fig. 18 - Step 1. Add Language

Step 2. The language is shown at the bottom of the list in the *Language Manager*, and as explained before, it is possible to manage it through the various buttons.

Fig. 19 - Step 2. Add Language

3.1.2. Search the lexicon

3.1.2.1. General search

The search bar enables the browsing of lexical entries according to different parameters:

- **Starts:** you search all the entries that start with the string you typed.
- **Contains:** you search all the entries that contain the string you typed in the bar.
- **Equals:** you search all the entries that are exactly as the string you typed in the bar.
- **Ends:** you search all the entries that end with the string you typed in the bar.

Fig. 20 - Lexicon General Search

3.1.2.2. Filtered search

The *filter icon* enables a more detailed search, allowing it by:

- **Type:** you search by type of lexical entry (e.g. word, etymon, cognate, etc.).
- **Pos:** you search by Part of speech.
- **Entry:** you search by entry or flexed.
- **Author:** you search by the author of the lexical entry, which means, the editor who was responsible for adding the new entry.
- **Language:** you search by language.
- **Status:** you search by the status of the lexical entry (*working, completed, or reviewed*).

Each of the parameters' search boxes will open a scrolling window by clicking on the harrow on the right. Each window will include all the possible choices. The red box with a *reset icon* provides a search example within a pop-up window.

Fig. 21 - Lexicon Filtered Search

The example shown in [Figure 21](#) shows how you can filter a search including all the words in *Oscan* which are verbs and whose status is *working*.

3.1.2.3. Switch to ID view

The *label view icon* disables the label view and automatically switches to ID view, which shows the lexical entry and its tree through its IDs and URI.

The procedure for the search is the same as the one shown in the paragraphs before. [Figure 22](#) and [Figure 23](#) show only the different interfaces.

Fig. 22 - Lexical entry view

Fig. 23 - Label view

3.1.3. Add lexical entry

This section reports the steps to add a new lexical entry to the platform. Keep in mind that the addition of a new lexical entry is directly linked with the opening of the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. The example shows the addition of the Oscan word *via*.

Step 1. From *Column A*, *Lexicon Panel*, click on **+** which allows you to add a new lexical entry. It will automatically and immediately create a new lexical entry, shown and opened in *Column B*, *Core Panel*. A green message will be shown to inform you that the lexical entry is created. Keep in mind that the lexical entry created always has a label starting with “LexO”, as shown in the *Core Panel* and in the *Lexicon Panel*.

Fig. 24 - Step 1. Add lexical entry

Fig. 25 - Step 1. Add lexical entry

Step 2. Given the label provided, the second thing to do is to immediately change the label of the lexical entry with the label you need, in order to have a correct lexical entry in the *Lexicon Panel*. The label is changed by simply writing on the *Label* corresponding bar.

Fig. 26 - Step 2. Add lexical entry

Step 3. General and morphological information about the lexical entry can be managed directly in this section as shown in the next paragraphs.

3.1.4. Manage lexical entry

3.1.4.1. General information management

All the general and morphological information about the lexical entry can be managed (deleted, modified, etc.) by writing on the specific bars, selecting new options on the scrolling window, checking the box, or switching the toggle button. Details and examples are reported below for the Oscan word *vía*, searched and select from the *Lexicon Panel*, *Column A*, and opened in the *Core Panel* on *Column B*, as shown the [Figure 27](#).

Edit the label

The label of the lexical entry can be changed by typing in the corresponding bar. As stated before, the label is the one that appears in the *Lexicon Panel* on *Column A*, therefore it is fundamental to change it immediately whenever adding a new lexical entry because as default the label for a new lexical entry is its corresponding URL. The modification and changes in the label are automatically saved and updated through the *Core Panel*.

Etymon marking

If a lexical entry is an etymon, it is possible to state this information by using the corresponding toggle button. By default the toggle button is off, if clicked, it turns blue and the lexical entry is marked as an etymon. It is possible to change it back by clicking it again, the button will change back again the color.

Degree of certainty marking

If the attestation of a specific lexical entry is not certain, it is possible to mark this information thanks to the specific check box next to *Uncertain*. If clicked it changes color to blue. It is possible to change it back by clicking it again, the button will change back again the color.

Type

The type of the lexical entry can be selected through a list in a scrolling window that appears in the corresponding bar. The types available refer to the *Core Model* classes of OntoLex-Lemon: *(single) words*, *multiword expressions*, and *affixes*. Keep in mind that if a lexical entry is marked as an etymon through the toggle button, the *Type* bar disappears.

Language selection

The language of a lexical entry can be selected through a list of languages available in EpiLexO in a scrolling window that appears in the corresponding bar. Adding a lexical entry to a language rather than another is a fundamental action since it means adding it to a specific corpus rather than another. EpiLexO provides multilingual resources but each of them is distinguished to one another.

Add the stem type

The stem type of the lexical entry can be changed by typing in the corresponding bar. Changes in the stem type are automatically saved and updated through the *Core Panel*, if you need to delete the stem type, just simply cancel the entire item in the bar.

Change the status

The status of the lexical entry can be changed by clicking on the *status icon* ● on the grey bar, on the far right of the *Core Panel*. The icon will change color (red: working/work in progress; yellow: completed; green: reviewed) just by clicking on it and it will also automatically change the status shown in the *Lexicon Panel* on *Column A*.

Fig. 27 - Manage lexical entry

3.1.4.2. Morphology management

From the *Core Panel* it is also possible to manage specific and detailed morphological information, in the **Morphology** section. By default, it is provided the Part of Speech information. Yet, by clicking on **+** you can add other morphological traits together with their specific values. You do so by selecting them in the scrolling window. Keep in mind that the value options (and scrolling window) are dynamically dependent on the traits option. For example, if selecting the trait “gender” the value will show “common gender, masculine, etc.”. Yet, if I select “degree” as a trait, the value options will be: “positive”, “superlative” etc. The *question mark icon* **?** gives an automatic explanation of the meaning of the trait when passing on the icon with the cursor. The red *delete icon* **🗑** allows to deletion of a single new morphological trait. Details and examples are reported below for the Oscan word *vía*, searched and select from the *Lexicon Panel, Column A*, and opened in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*.

Fig. 28 - Morphology management

3.1.4.3. Add lexical concept to lexical entry

Step 1. From the *Core Panel* of a lexical entry, look for the *evokes box*, press **+** and search for a specific lexical concept on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the results (lexical concept) available on the platform.

Step 2. Select the lexical concept you want to link to the lexical entry. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform. By doing that a lexical concept will be automatically linked to the lexical entry you managing. With the **🗑** the lexical concept can be deleted.

Step 3. At this point, the lexical entry should appear in the lexical concept *is evoked by box*. In the actual example, in the *Core Panel* of the lexical concept of *Agriculture & Vegetation* there is the specific sense of the Oscan lexical entry *vía*.

Fig. 29 - Step 1. Add lexical concept to lexical entry

Fig. 30 - Step 3. Add lexical concept to lexical entry

3.1.4.4. Add cognate to lexical entry

A fundamental information that can be provided in the *Core Panel* of a lexical entry, is the presence or not of cognates. We can provide this information by creating a link with another lexical entry outside or inside the platform in a specific section in the *Core Panel*: **Cognate**⁵. A lexical entry can be linked to its cognate which can be: **a.** another lexical entry available in the platform; **b.** an external entry available in other repositories such as the *LiLa Lemma Bank* in two different ways: **1.** by enabling the search on the LiLa endpoint; **2.** by copy-pasting the URL of the external resource element one wants to link to. Steps are shown below through the example of the Oscan verb *upsed* and its Paelignan cognate *upsaseter*, and its cognate from the Latin word *opus* selected from *LiLa Lemma Bank*.

⁵ Reference to the OntoLex-Lemon relations isCognate

Internal cognate

Step 1. As shown in [Figure 31](#), search for a lexical entry in *Column A, Lexicon Panel* through the *Search bar*. The results are shown on the list of lexical entries available on EpiLexO. Select the lexical entry you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Core Panel*. Look for the *Cognate box*, press **+** and search for a specific cognate on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the results (lexical entries from the languages rather than one of the lexical entries) available on the platform.

Fig. 31 - Step 1. Add internal cognate

Fig. 32 - Step 2. Add internal cognate

Step 2. Select the cognate you want to link to the lexical entry. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying “Cognates changed correctly”. By doing that a cognate will be automatically created for the lexical entry, which means an internal link

between lexical entries from 2 different languages will be generated. In fact, will be shown in blue. See [Figure 32](#) above.

Step 3. Clicking on will provide the *Core Panel* window of the specific cognate of the lexical entry. As shown in [Figure 33](#) below, we linked the cognate of the Oscan *upsed*: the Paelignan verb *upsaseter*.

Fig. 33 - Step 3. Add internal cognate

External cognate: by LiLa Endpoint

Step 1. Search for a lexical entry in *Column A, Lexicon Panel* through the *Search bar*. The results are shown on the list of lexical entries available on EpiLexO. As [Figure 34](#) shows you can select the lexical entry you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Core Panel*. Look for the *Cognate box*, press **+** and click on the to enable the LiLa endpoint search (the icon will turn green, as explained elsewhere), then type the cognate you want to link in the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the matching entries available from which the scholar may choose (lemmas available on the LiLa Lemma Bank as *opus*, *opusculum*, etc.).

Step 2. Select the cognate you want to link to the lexical entry. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying “Cognates changed correctly”. By doing that a cognate will be automatically created for the lexical entry, which means an external link between the lexical entry and LiLa will be generated. In fact, the will be shown in blue as in [Figure 35](#).

Step 3. Clicking on the will provide the specific cognate of the lexical entry in a new tab. Specifically, it will open a LiLa website page referring to the cognate you just linked. As shown in the Figure below, we linked a cognate of the Oscan *upsed*: the Latin verb *opus*, from LiLa. Shown in [Figure 36](#).

Fig. 34 - Step 1. Add external cognate by LiLa Endpoint

Fig. 35 - Step 2. Add external cognate by LiLa Endpoint

Fig. 36 - Step 3. Add external cognate by LiLa Endpoint

External cognate: by copy-pasting URL

Step 1. Search for a lexical entry in *Column A, Lexicon Panel* through the *Search bar*. The results are shown on the list of lexical entries available on EpiLexO. Select the lexical entry you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Core Panel*. Look for the *Cognate box*, press **+** and click on the checkbox to enable the copy-pasting functionality.

Fig. 37 - Step 1. Add external cognate by copy-pasting URL

Step 2. Paste on the bar a specific URL precedently copied from an external source (it can be LiLa). A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying "Label changed correctly". By doing that a cognate will be automatically created for the lexical entry, which means an external link between the lexical entry and LiLa will be generated.

Fig. 38 - Step 2. Add external cognate by copy-pasting URL

Step 3. Clicking on the blue will provide the LiLa page of *opus* in a new tab. As shown in [Figure 38](#) above, we linked the cognate of the Oscan *upsed*: the Latin verb *opus*.

3.1.5. Enrich the lexical entry

This section reports the steps to enrich the lexical entry, which means: **a.** add a new form, **b.** add a new sense; **c.** add a new etymology. The example shows the enrichment of the Oscan word *via*.

3.1.5.1. Add new form

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Click on **+** at the bottom of the page and select *Add form*.

Step 2. A green message will be displayed on the top right of the page and the *Core Panel* will automatically change into the form created. This *Core Panel* provides all the general and morphological information about the form, distinguished in:

- **Inheritance:** provides the info of a form that are inherited from the lexical entry. For example, if a lexical entry is a noun, the form would be a noun as well). In fact, this section provides by default *partOfSpeech* information, which is indeed blocked.
- **Type:** a scrolling window referring to the type of forms (*OntoLex-Lemon model: canonicalForm, lexicalForm, otherForm*).
- **Uncertain:** a checkbox which can be checked whenever the form is certain.
- **Other representation:** referring to different representations of forms (*writtenRep* as default).
- **Morphology:** provides morphological information with different traits.

The grey top bar and the grey bottom bar show the same sentence found in the lexical entry, which explains when the form was created, at what time, by who, and when it was lastly

updated. The automatic label generated for the new form is always a URI, as shown in the figure below. In fact, it is important to immediately change it to the one needed, so that it will be correctly shown on the *Lexical tree* of the lexical entry in the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*.

Step 3. Manage all the detailed information about the form from here as shown in the next paragraphs. The blue *delete icon* allows you to delete the entire form.

Fig. 39 - Step 1. Add new form

Fig. 40 - Step 2. Add new form

Fig. 41 - Step 2. Add new form

Inheritance information management

This general information about the form cannot be managed or changed in the specific **Inheritance** section. By default, Part of speech is provided.

Type changing

With the scrolling window is possible to select the option of lexical form type. The *question mark icon* ? gives an automatic explanation in a pop-up window.

Degree of certainty marking

If the form is not certain, it is possible to mark this information thanks to the check box next to *Uncertain*. If clicked it changes color to blue. It is possible to change it back by clicking it again, the button will change back again the color.

Fig. 42 - Form information management

Add other representations

For the representations of the forms of the lexical entry, there is the **Other representation** section, and, since the default provided is *writtenRep*, with **+** you can add new representations by selecting the trait from the scrolling window, and writing the value on the writing bar. The red *delete icon* allows you to deletion of each representation.

Fig. 43 - Add other representations

Morphology management

From the *Core Panel* it is also possible to manage specific and detailed morphological information, in the **Morphology** section. By clicking on **+** you can add morphological traits together with their specific values. You do so by selecting them in the scrolling window. Keep in mind that the value options (and scrolling window) are dynamically dependent on the traits option. (as stated before in the previous paragraph). The *question mark icon* **?** gives an automatic explanation of the meaning of the trait when passing on the icon with the cursor. The red *delete icon* allows to deletion of a single new morphological trait.

3.1.5.2. Add new sense

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Click on **+** at the bottom of the page and select *Add Sense*.

Step 2. A green message will be displayed on the top right of the page and the *Core Panel* will automatically change into the sense created. It provides information about the sense, distinguished in:

- **Definitions:** shows the definitions of the sense.
- **Lexical concept:** shows the lexical concept of the sense.

Fig. 44 - Step 1. Add new sense

The grey top bar and the grey bottom bar show the same sentence found in the lexical entry, which explains when the sense was created, at what time, and by who, and when it was lastly updated. When creating a new sense its label (shown in the *Lexicon Tree* in *Column A*) corresponds to its definition. As shown from the figure, it is automatically generated as “no definition”. In fact, it is important to immediately change it to the one needed, so that it will be correctly shown on the *Lexical tree* of the lexical entry in the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*.

Fig. 45 - Step 2. Add new sense

Fig. 46 - Step 2. Add new sense

Step 3. Manage all the detailed information about the sense from this *Core Panel*, as for the lexical entry section mentioned before (e.g. selecting new options on the scrolling window, checking the box or switching the toggle button, writing on bars).

Fig. 47 - Manage sense information

Add definition

From the *Core Panel* of a sense, it is possible to manage definitions, by writing on the specific bar. By default, it only provides the *definition* of the sense, which also corresponds to the label of the sense itself. With the *add icon* + it is possible to add new traits by selecting the traits from the scrolling window, and writing the value on the writing bar. The red *delete icon* 🗑️ allows you to deletion of each representation.

Degree of certainty marking

If the sense is not certain, it is possible to mark this information thanks to the check box next to *Uncertain*. If clicked it changes color to blue. It is possible to change it back by clicking it again, the button will change back again the color.

Add lexical concept to sense

A sense of a lexical entry can sometimes evoke a mental concept. With the platform, it is possible to link the sense to a specific lexical concept (see *Lexical Concept Panel*).

Step 1. From the *Core Panel* of a sense, look for the *Lexical Concept box*, press **+** and search for a specific lexical concept on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the results (lexical concept) available on the platform.

Step 2. Select the lexical concept you want to link to the lexical entry. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform. By doing that a sense will be automatically linked to its corresponding lexical concept.

Fig. 48 - Step 2. Add lexical concept to sense

Step 3. At this point, the lexical entry (and its sense) should appear in the lexical concept *lexicalized senses box*. In the actual example, in the *Core Panel* of the lexical concept *Animals* there is the specific sense of the Oscan lexical entry *via*.

Fig. 49 - Step 3. Add lexical concept to sense

3.1.5.3. Add new etymology

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Click on **+** at the bottom of the page and select *Add etymology*.

Fig. 50 - Step 1. Add new etymology

Step 2. It will open the *Etymology Panel* in *Column B*, next to the *Core Panel* which provides information about the etymology, distinguished in:

- **Label:** shows the label of the etymology.
- **Author:** shows the author responsible for the creation of the etymon.
- **Uncertain:** a checkbox that can be checked whenever the etymon is certain.

The grey top bar and the grey bottom bar show the same sentence found in the lexical entry, which explains when the etymology was created, at what time and by who, and when it was lastly updated. The automatic label generated for the new *Etymology* is a *Etymology of: via* in the specific bar in the *Etymology Panel*, and a corresponding URI in the Lexicon tree, as shown in the figure below.

In fact, it is important to immediately change it to the one needed, so that it will be correctly shown on the *Lexical tree* of the lexical entry in the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*. Once the label is changed, a green message should appear.

Fig. 51 - Step 2. Add new etymology

Fig. 52 - Step 2. Add new etymology

Step 3. Manage all the detailed information about the etymology from this *Etymology Panel* and add Etylinks by clicking on the *add icon*. The management of all the information are explained below. The *delete icon* allows you to delete the entire etymology.

Edit the label

The label of the etymology can be changed by typing in the corresponding bar. As stated before, the label is the one that appears in the *Lexicon Panel* on *Column A*, therefore it is fundamental to change it immediately whenever adding a new lexical entry because as default the label for a new lexical entry is *Etymology of: [lexical entry]*. The modification and changes in the label are automatically saved and updated through the *Core Panel*.

Edit the Author

The author refers to the user responsible for the creation and modification of the etymology. It can be changed or added by writing on the corresponding bar.

Degree of certainty marking

If the etymology is not certain, it is possible to mark this information thanks to the check box next to *Uncertain*. If clicked it changes color to blue. It is possible to change it back by clicking it again, the button will change back again the color.

Fig. 53 - Manage etymology information

Add EtyLinks

The etymology can be linked to its etymon, which is an external entry available in other repositories such as the LiLa Etymological Dictionary, in two different ways: **1.** by enabling the search on the LiLa endpoint; **2.** by copy-pasting the `URL` of the external resource element one wants to link to. Steps are shown below through the example of the PIE root **h3ep* from the LiLa Etymological Dictionary which is selected as the etymon of the Oscan *upsed*.

Etymology: by LiLa Endpoint

Step 1. Search for a lexical entry in *Column A, Lexicon Panel* through the *Search bar*. The results are shown on the list of lexical entries available on EpiLexO. Select the etymology of the lexical entry you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Etymology Panel*, next to *Core Panel*. In this section, click **+** to add an *Etylink box*. The boxes are named “*Etylink*” + *ordinal number* and provide info⁶ about:

- **Etymon:** a bar where the external resource of the etymology can be searched (or the URL can be pasted).
- **EtyLink Type:** a scrolling window with 2 options (inheritance or borrowing).
- **EtySource:** a blocked bar that shows the URI of the Etymon.
- **EtyTarget:** a blocked bar that shows the URI of the lexical entry that we are managing.
- **Note:** a writing section to write a note.

Fig. 54 - Step 1. Add etylink by LiLa Endpoint

Step 2. From the box, enable the (the icon will turn green, as explained elsewhere), and type the PIE root you need on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the matching entries available from which the scholar may choose (roots available on the LiLa Etymological Dictionary).

⁶ In reference to the `lemonEty` Model of Ontolex-Lemon (F. Khan, 2018)

Fig. 55 - Step 2. Add etylink by LiLa Endpoint

Step 3. Select the root you want to link to the etymology of the lexical entry. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying “Etylink source updated”. By doing that the external link between the etymology and LiLa will be generated. Once the linking is generated it is possible to open the external resource page through the .

Fig. 56 - Step 3. Add etylink by LiLa Endpoint

Etymology: by copy-pasting URL

Step 1. Search for a lexical entry in *Column A, Lexicon Panel* through the *Search bar*. The results are shown on the list of lexical entries available on EpiLexO. Select the etymology of the lexical entry you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Etymology Panel*, next to *Core*

Panel. Click **+** to add an *Etylink box* (describe before). From here, click on the checkbox to enable the copy-pasting functionality (as explained elsewhere).

Fig. 57 - Step 1. Add etylink by copy-pasting URL

Step 2. Paste on the bar a specific URL precedently copied from an external source. A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform. By doing that an external link between the etymology and LiLa will be generated. Once the link is generated it is possible to open the external resource page through the .

Fig. 58 - Step 2. Add etylink by copy-pasting URL

3.1.6. Add external bibliographical reference

This section discusses how bibliographical references to relevant literature can be added to lexical entries, forms, senses, or etymologies via a Zotero plug-in. The example reported below is about the Oscan lexical entry *vía*, yet the bibliographic reference links are totally casual and only for demonstrational purposes. The steps reported are the same for forms, entries, or etymologies.

Step 1. Select the lexical entry⁷ needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Click on **+** at the bottom of the page in the green box of the *Core Panel*, and select *Add bibliography*.

Fig. 59 - Step 1. Add external bibliographic reference

Step 2. Once clicked, it will open the **Zotero window** showing the list of all the bibliographical references available in the general Bibliography: *Library of PRIN Italia Antica*⁸. The Bibliography window is organized in a table with 3 columns:

1. **Title:** the title of the bibliographical text.
2. **Creator:** the author of the text.
3. **Date:** the date of the text.

By clicking on a reference, the window will show more details about the bibliography selected in the right part of the window as item type, title, author, editor, pages, issues, publication date, abstract, and URL. Select the needed bibliographic reference and by pressing the Save button it will automatically add it to the lexical entry.

⁷ If you want to add a bibliographical reference on a form, sense, or etymology you need to select the specific item from the *Lexicon tree, Lexicon Panel, Column A* which will be opened in *Column B*.

⁸ https://www.zotero.org/groups/2552746/prin_italia_antica/library

Fig. 60 - Step 2. Add external bibliographic reference

Step 3. A green message will be shown on the top right corner of the platform, and the bibliographic reference will be stored in the *Bibliographic Panel* in *Column C*, from where it will be possible to open the Zotero Library with and the reference source page in a new tab with , as shown below. The *synchronize icon* synchronize - update - the Zotero Library (useful in case of changes, uploadings, etc.).

Fig. 61 - Step 3. Add external bibliographic reference

Fig. 62 - Step 3. Add external bibliographic reference

The screenshot shows the Zotero web interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with 'Other Group Libraries' and a tree view for 'PRIN Italia Antica' containing categories like Archaeology, Faliscan, and Venetic. The main area displays a list of references with columns for Title, Creator, and Date. The selected reference is '¿Hablantes de lenguas Itálicas en hispania? un análisis onomástico y sociolingüístico de la epigrafía latina hispana del siglo II A.C.' by Estarán Tolosa. On the right, a detailed view of this article is shown, including its title, author (Estarán Tolosa, María José), publication (Athenaeum), volume (107), issue (2), pages (388-423), date (2019), and a URL. An abstract is also visible, discussing the onomastic and sociolinguistic approach to the Latinization of the Iberian Peninsula.

Fig. 63 - Step 3. Add external bibliographic reference

The screenshot shows the header of the ZAGUAN (Universidad de Zaragoza Repository) website. It features the university's logo and name, the repository name 'ZAGUAN Universidad de Zaragoza Repository', and navigation links for 'ESTUDIOS', 'I+D+i', 'INSTITUCIÓN', 'INTERNACIONAL', and 'VIDA UNIVERSITARIA'. Below the header, there are options to 'Submit', 'Personalize', and 'Help', along with language selection 'EN / ES'.

Home > Articles > ¿Hablantes de lenguas Itálicas en Hispania? un análisis onomástico y sociolingüístico de la epigrafía latina hispana del siglo II A.C.

The screenshot shows the article page for '¿Hablantes de lenguas Itálicas en Hispania? un análisis onomástico y sociolingüístico de la epigrafía latina hispana del siglo II A.C.' by Estarán Tolosa, M.J. (Universidad de Zaragoza). The page includes a thumbnail of the journal cover (Athenaeum), a detailed abstract, and metadata such as the language (Español), year (2019), and publication information (Athenaeum 2019, 2 (2019), 388-423). The abstract discusses the identification of individuals from Italic-speaking areas based on onomastic analysis of personal names in Latin inscriptions.

Step 4. You can manage the bibliographic information from this panel. In fact, By clicking on a reference, it shows more detailed info such as *Title*, *Author*, *Date*, and others that can be directly enriched as *Notes* and *Pages*.

3.1.7. Add notes

Notes are managed directly from *Note Panel* in *Column C*: the writing bar allows you to change the text of the notes, add words, manage the formatting of the words, and even clear them by clicking on the *reset icon* ✕. As already mentioned, the columns and panels are dynamically adaptive, in fact, the *Note Panel* shows different notes according to the item you selected from *Column A*. The example below shows the adding of a note of the Oscan lexical entry *via*, yet the same procedure can be followed for the adding of forms, senses, and etymologies.

Fig. 64 - Add notes

Select the lexical entry from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, and write the note in the bar in the *Note Panel* in *Column C*. A green message will be shown and a *note icon* 🗨️ will appear in the *Lexicon Tree* in *Column A*.

3.1.8. General linking functionalities

This section shows how it is possible to also create other internal and external links through the *Link Panel* in *Column C*. As explained in *Link Panel* section before, has two different sections: **a.** the See Also: which enables linking lexical entries⁹ with similar properties available in the platform (internal linking), or from external resources (external linking); **b.** the Same As: which enables linking with other lexical entries with equal traits from other sources (external link).

Regarding external linking, it is possible to have two different modalities: **a.** by the copy-pasting of an URL; **b.** or by the LiLa endpoint button. The latter is only allowed if a lexical entry is a root. The *add icon* + adds more *Same as* or *See Also* items. The *delete icon* 🗑️ allows the deletion of the items. Examples are shown below for the Oscan lexical entry *upsed* and for the **ali-tero-s* PIE root.

⁹ If you want to add a link on a form, sense, or etymology you need to select the specific item from the *Lexicon tree*, *Lexicon Panel*, *Column A* which will be opened in *Column B*. And the procedure would be the same as the one explained in the example for lexical entry.

3.1.8.1. SeeAlso

See Also: Internal linking

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Then, open the *Link Panel* in *Column C*. Click on the **+** of the *See Also* box and type in the search bar the lexical entry you are trying to link.

Step 2. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the matching entries available in the platform from which the scholar may choose. Select the entry you want to link. By doing that an internal link will be automatically generated.

Fig. 65 - Add SeeAlso: internal linking

See Also: External linking - by copy-pasting URL

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Then, open the *Link Panel* in *Column C*. Click on the **+** of the *See Also* box and click on the checkbox to enable the copy-pasting functionality.

Step 2. Paste on the bar a specific URL precedently copied from an external source (it can be LiLa). A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying “SeeAlso updated”. By doing that an external link between the lexical entry and LiLa will be generated.

Fig. 66 - Add SeeAlso: external linking

3.1.8.2. SameAs

Same As: External linking - by copy-pasting URL

Step 1. Select the lexical entry needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Then, open the *Link Panel* in *Column C*. Click on the **+** of the *Same As* box and click on the checkbox to enable the copy-pasting functionality.

Step 2. Paste on the bar a specific URL precedently copied from an external source (it can be LiLa). A green message box will be shown on the top right of the platform saying “SeeAlso updated”. By doing that an external link between the lexical entry and LiLa will be generated. Once the linking is generated it is possible to open the external resource page through the .

Fig. 67 - Add SameAs: external linking. Copy-pasting URL

Same As: External linking - by LiLa Endpoint

⚠ This functionality is enabled only for lexical entries which are roots (PIE or Pit).

Step 1. Select the lexical entry (root, shown with *) needed from the *Lexicon Panel* in *Column A*, it will be displayed in the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. Then, open the *Link Panel* in *Column C*. Click on the **+** of the *Same As* box and enable the **🔗** (the icon will turn green, as explained elsewhere).

Step 2. Type the lemma you need in the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the matching entries available from which the scholar may choose (roots available on the LiLa Etymological Dictionary). Once the linking is generated it is possible to open the external resource page through the **🔗**.

Fig. 68 - Add SameAs: external linking. By LiLa Endpoint

3.1.9. Export Lexicon

Fig. 69 - Export Lexicon

From *Column A*, *Lexicon Panel*, press the *export icon* **📄** which exports the entire lexicon.

3.2. Inscriptions Functionalities

3.2.1. Add new folder

Step 1. From *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, press the *add icon* **+** which will open an option window. Press on *Add new folder*: a folder will be automatically added to the *Inscriptions Panel*, and a blue message will appear on the top right of the platform.

Step 2. The new folder will be placed at the end of the inscriptions list with the name “*new-folder-*” followed by an ordinal number. Rename the folder by clicking on the folder itself and selecting the option *Rename Folder*.

Step 3. The folder can be managed with the other options, as shown in [Figure 70](#). For example, it is possible to delete the folder, add new folders inside the one created, to add or create empty files, by clicking on the document itself which will open an options window. Also, the folder can be moved by selecting it and transporting it with the cursor to another part of the *Inscriptions Panel* list (e.g. inside another folder, etc.)

Fig. 70 - Add new folder and management

3.2.2. Import new file (inscription)

This section reports the steps to import a text (inscription) into the platform. Keep in mind that the addition of a new inscription is directly linked with the opening of the *Epigraphy Panel* in *Column B*.

Step 1. As shown in [Figure 71](#), From *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, press the *add icon* **+** which will open an option window. Press on *Add new file*: a TEI/Epidoc XML document -

precedently annotated - can be selected from your device, and it will be automatically added to the *Inscriptions Panel*, and a blue message will appear on the top right of the platform.

! With the same exact procedure it is possible to add **more than one file at the time**. From your device, you can select through the window, all the TEI/Epidoc XML documents you want at the same time. They will be all added to the platform simultaneously.

Fig. 71 - Step 1. Import new file

Step 2. The new document will be placed at the end of the inscriptions list with its original name. The inscription will be automatically displayed on the *Epigraphy Panel* in *Column B*, and all the supplementary information about the inscription as metadata is shown in *Column C, Metadata Panel*.

Step 3. The file can be managed by the other options, as shown in [Figure 72](#). For example, it is possible to delete, copy, rename, or download the file. It is also possible to upload the metadata of the Epidoc document (see [3.2.3 Update the inscription Metadata](#)), by clicking on the document itself which will open an options window. Also, the file can be moved by selecting it and transporting it with the cursor to another part of the *Inscriptions Panel* list (e.g. inside another folder, etc.)

Fig. 72 - Step 3. Import new file

3.2.3. Update the inscription Metadata

Through the platform it is possible to change the metadata of a specific inscription. Each XML document, precedently annotated in TEI/EpiDoc contains accessory information about the edition, the epigraphy, and the text such as the year of discovery, the editor, the writing system, etc. All that information is displayed in the *Metadata Panel*, yet it can be modified by uploading a new XML document to the platform through the *Inscriptions Panel*. The steps are reported below. Keep in mind that it is not possible to directly change metadata through the platform, yet metadata is previously changed locally by managing the XML document itself.

Step 1. From *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, click on the XML document and it will open an options window. Click on the option *Update Document (metadata only)*: the same TEI/EpiDoc XML document - precedently annotated, and modified - can be selected from your device, and it will automatically replace the original XML document. A blue message will appear on the top right of the platform. Keep in mind that the modified XML should have the same name as the one it is replacing¹⁰. Shown in [Figure 73](#).

Step 2. The modified will be automatically displayed on the *Epigraphy Panel* in *Column B*, and all the supplementary - and modified - metadata is shown in *Column C, Metadata Panel*. The example shows the modification of the *ItAnt_Oscan_10* in the metadata regarding the edition. In particular, the editor “Marianosaria Zinzi” is changed to “Test”.

¹⁰ Check Troubleshooting section for recurring errors with metadata uploading

Fig. 73 - Step 1. Update inscription metadata

Fig. 74 - Step 2. Update inscription metadata

3.2.4. Download XML (inscription)

Step 1. From *Column A*, *Inscriptions Panel*, click on the XML document and it will open an options window. Click on the option *Download File* (see the window in [Figure 73](#)). The file will be automatically downloaded on your device, and a blue message on the top right of the platform will be shown.

3.2.5. Create Empty File

Empty files are a solution we implemented to allow researchers to add attestations of forms in non-ItAnt inscriptions. For this reason, they can create an inscription which does not have an XML file linked to it. For this kind of file, the inscription is empty, which means that the *Epigraphy Panel* does not show any information. Tokens, usually shown at the top of the *Epigraphy Panel*, are manually added by the researcher while creating attestations of forms. For a detailed description and information of the procedure see [3.2.7.2 Create attestation for Empty Files](#).

Step 1. From *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, press the *add icon* **+** which will open an option window. Press on *Create empty file*: a wizard window will be automatically opened. From this window you can choose: the title of the empty inscription and the folder where to place it¹¹. Click on the green and the empty file will be automatically displayed on the *Epigraphy Panel* in *Column B*.

Fig. 75 - Step 1. Create empty file

Step 2. From the *Epigraphy Panel* in *Column B*, it will be possible to add token (and corresponding attestation) by clicking on the **+**, which will be automatically shown in a list in the *Attestation Panel* on *Column C*. Tokens are shown vertically in the *Epigraphy Panel*.

Step 3. The empty file can be managed by the other options, as for ItAnt (XML) documents as explained in [3.2.2. Import new file \(inscription\)](#).

¹¹ *Root* refers to the top-level directory of the folder structure. This directory includes all other directories/folders and various files.

3.2.6. Search the inscriptions

3.2.6.1. General search

Fig. 76 - Inscription General Search

The search bar enables a textual search for the name of the inscription by *Starts* or *Contains*. The example shows how the bar shows all the inscriptions that contain the string “Osc”. Keep in mind that the search bar is uppercase-independent.

3.2.7. Create attestation

From *Column B, Ephigraphy Panel, Text linker* it is possible to create a connection between text parts (i.e. token in our case) and lexical elements (i.e. forms). Linking a word in the text with a form in the lexicon in fact equals creating an attestation for that form. A user can make an attestation, in the sense that he can associate a selected token with a specific lexical entry form. Attestations can be created for ItAnt inscriptions (XML) or empty files.

Attestations can be visualized in list in the *Attestation Panel* in *Column C*. You can visualize:

- all the attestations of a specific form by simply selecting a form of a lexical entry in *Lexicon Panel, Column A*. The *Attestation Panel* will be opened automatically.
- all the attestations of all the forms included in an inscription by simply selecting - and opening - an inscription in *Inscription Panel, Column A*. The *Attestation Panel* will be opened automatically.

3.2.7.1. Create attestation for ItAnt inscriptions (XML)

Two are the options:

- a. the token is an attestation of a form already present on EpiLexO;
- b. EpiLexo does not recognize that token as a form of a specific lexical entry available on the server, and there are no lexical entries to select from.

In the first case, it opens a scrolling window that shows all the forms of lexical entries already available on the platform that are somehow recognized as possibly linked with the selected token. In the second case, if no forms are recognized, you are allowed to add a new form from scratch. The scrolling window opened allows you to add a new item, and if clicked, it

opens a **Wizard window** that shows 2 possibilities: **a.** Create new lexical entry; **b.** Choose one existing lexical entry.

Fig. 77 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a horizontal line. The main content area contains the text: "To create a new lexical form it is necessary to have a reference lexical entry. Select one of the two options:". Below this text are two radio buttons: "Create new lexical entry" (which is selected) and "Choose one existing lexical entry". At the bottom right of the window, there are two buttons: "Previous" and "Next".

By selecting **Create new lexical entry**, a new window is opened that allows you to enter the basic information: morphological information (*Type, Language, PoS*) can be added through the scrolling windows (**Figure 78**), and a label can be added through the specific bar (*Label*).

Fig. 78 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a horizontal line. The main content area contains the text: "Enter basic info for lexical entry creation:". Below this text are four input fields: "Label" (a text box), "Type" (a dropdown menu with "Select type" selected), "Language" (a dropdown menu with "Select lang" selected), and "Part of Speech" (a dropdown menu with "Select pos" selected). At the bottom right of the window, there are two buttons: "Previous" and "Next".

Fig. 79 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a horizontal line. The main content area contains the text: "Enter basic info for form creation:". Below this text are two input fields: "Written Form" (a text box) and "Type" (a dropdown menu with "Select type" selected). At the bottom right of the window, there are two buttons: "Previous" and "Next".

After clicking on the **Next button**, it opens another window to further add new basic info (**Figure 80**), and then another window is opened which shows a summary of the new form.

Fig. 80 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a horizontal line. The main content area contains the text: "Summary:". Below this text are two lines of information: "Lexical form to create" followed by "hhh - http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/ontolex#canonicalForm" and "New lexical entry to be attached" followed by "heleviis". At the bottom right of the window, there are two buttons: "Previous" and "Proceed".

After clicking on the *Proceed button*, the last step is a page that shows the loading of the form and all the operations needed to upload it.

Fig. 81 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a section labeled "Summary:" followed by a list of ten steps, each with a green checkmark to its right, indicating completion:

- Lexical entry creation
- Attaching language
- Attaching type
- Attaching label
- Attaching part of speech
- Creating form
- Attaching written form property
- Attaching type property
- Finish

At the bottom right of the window, there is a "Close" button.

By selecting **Choose one existing lexical entry**, a new window is opened that allows you to select an existing lexical entry, which can be searched by typing on the bar and selecting from the options provided.

Fig. 82 - Wizard window

The screenshot shows a window titled "Wizard" with a close button (x) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a JSON object: `{"lexicalEntry": ""}`. Underneath, the text "Choose a lexical entry:" is followed by a search input field and a red "Clear" button. At the bottom of the window, there are "Previous" and "Next" buttons.

When selecting the lexical entry, the procedure is the same as shown before: basic information, label managing, summary, and proceed box.

Attestation of a form already available on EpiLexO

Step 1. Select an inscription from *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, which will be opened on *Column B, Epigraphy Panel (Text Linker)*. In this section, click on a specific token to create an attestation. If EpiLexo recognizes that token as a form of a specific lexical entry available on the server, it will open a scrolling window with all the lexical entries' forms available.

Step 2. Select the form needed and it automatically creates an attestation of that lexical entry. An info message in a green box will be shown on the top right, and the attestation is reported in *Column C, Attestation Panel*.

Step 3. From *Column C, Attestation Panel* it is possible to manage the attestation or visualize detailed information about it. It is possible to:

- **Author:** write the author of the Attestation (the researcher who added the attestation in the platform)
- **Uncertain:** it allows to mark the uncertainty of the attestation

- **ExternalRef:** ?
- **Form:** shows the label of the form attested
- **Leiden:** shows the Leiden of the token (it should be the same as the one added in Step 1), yet it can be changed if needed
- **Lexical entry:** shows the URI of the lexical entry related to the form attested
- **Lexical entry label:** shows the label of the lexical entry related to the form attested
- **Note:** add eventual note about the attestation
- **Bibliography:** add a bibliographic reference

With it is possible to visualize widows reporting the *Core Panel* of the corresponding attested form, as shown in [Figure 85](#).

Fig. 83 - Step 1. Attestation of a form already available on EpiLexO

Fig. 84 - Step 2. Attestation of a form already available on EpiLexO

Fig. 85 - Step 3. Attestation of a form already available on EpiLexO

Attestation of a form not available on EpiLexO

Step 1. Select an inscription (Text) from *Column A, Inscriptions Panel*, which will be opened on *Column B, Epigraphy Panel*. From the *Linker*, click on a specific token to create an attestation. It will open a scrolling window with no lexical entry forms available. Click on “Add [token]”.

Fig. 86 - Step 1. Attestation of a form not available on EpiLexO

Step 2. The Wizard Window will automatically open and will allow you to create a form simply by following the steps on the Wizard Window, according to the 2 different possibilities shown before.

Fig. 87 - Step 2. Attestation of a form not available on EpiLexO

Step 3. Once the form needed is created from scratch, the attestation is automatically created. An info message in a green box will be shown on the top right, and the attestation is reported in *Column C, Attestation Panel*. From here, it is possible to manage the attestation or visualize detailed information about it, as shown in [Figure 85](#).

Fig. 88 - Step 2. Attestation of a form not available on EpiLexO

3.2.7.2. Create attestation for Empty Files

As mentioned in the sections above, empty files do not contain any token. In fact, to create an attestation, a researcher can manually add tokens at the moment they are adding

attestations. The list of tokens added will be shown in the *Epigraphy Panel* in vertical, in the order they are created.

Fig. 89 - Epigraphy Panel for Empty Files

Step 1. From *Column A, Inscription Panel*, select an empty file. It will be opened in the *Epigraphy Panel, Column B*. Press on **+** which will open a window. From the window, you simultaneously create a token (to be shown in the *Epigraphy Panel*) and its corresponding attestation. In our example, the form *upsed* (Leiden *upsed*) is attested in *Lu 1*.

Fig. 90 - Step 1. Attestation of a form in Empty File

Step 2. In the search bar, you can search for the corresponding form, which is attested in that inscription: by doing so you are creating an attestation. For our example, we write the Leiden (*upsed*), and we search for the corresponding form (*upsed*, Oscan, verb, singular, third person, past tense.). Pressing enter on your attestation is automatically created and it

will be shown in the *Attestation Panel*, *Column C*. Attestations are shown in the order you create them.

Step 3. From *Column C*, *Attestation Panel* it is possible to manage the attestation or visualize detailed information about it, as shown in [Figure 85](#), yet, to delete the attestation on empty file the situation is a little more complex.

Delete Attestation in Empty File

Step 1. From *Column A*, *Inscription Panel*, select an empty file that will be opened in the *Epigraphy Panel*, *Column B* showing all the tokens. The related attestations will be automatically opened in the *Attestation Panel*, *Column C*. Tokens and Attestations are linked.

Fig. 91 - Step 1. Delete attestation of a form in Empty File

Step 2. From the *Attestation Panel*, *Column C*, click on and the attestation will be deleted. By doing so, it will automatically delete the linked token in the *Epigraphy Panel*, *Column B*.

! There is also a available on each token in the *Epigraphy Panel*, *Column B*. If you delete the token, keep in mind that it won't automatically delete the related attestation. Yet, you have to delete it immediately through the *Attestation Panel* in *Column C*, as explained in **Step 2**.

3.3. Lexical concept Functionalities

3.3.1. Add lexical concept

This section reports the steps to add a new lexical concept to the platform. Keep in mind that the addition of a new lexical concept is directly linked with the opening of the *Core Panel* in *Column B*. The example shows the addition of the lexical concept *Time*.

Step 1. From *Column A, Lexical Concepts Panel*, click on **+** which allows you to add a new lexical concept, opened in *Column B, Core Panel*. A green message will be shown to inform you that the lexical concept is created.

Fig. 92 - Step 1. Add lexical concept

Step 2. The lexical concept created has always a specific label, as shown in [Figure 93](#). In fact, the second thing to do is to immediately change the label of the lexical concept with the label you need, in order to have a correct lexical concept in the *Lexical Concept Panel*. The label is changed by simply writing on the *Label* corresponding bar of the *Core Panel*.

Fig. 93 - Step 2. Add lexical concept

Step 3. The lexical concept information can be managed directly in the *Core Panel* as shown in the next paragraphs.

3.3.2. Delete lexical concept

There are 2 ways of creating child lexical concepts:

1. From *Column A*, *Lexical Concepts Panel*, click on a lexical concept, a window will be opened with different options. Select *Add Lexical Concept (child)*.

Fig. 94 - Option 1. Delete Lexical Concept

2. **Option 2.** From the *Core Panel* of *Column B* of a lexical concept, click on placed in the top grey bar of the panel.

Fig. 95 - Option 2. Delete Lexical Concept

⚠ In case, a lexical concept has one or more children, if you want to delete it, a warning message will appear in order to avoid making mistakes in deleting a lexical concept you did not mean to, as shown below.

Fig. 96 - Warning message - Delete Lexical Concept

3.3.3. Manage lexical concept

3.3.3.1. Edit the label

The label of the lexical concept can be changed by typing in the corresponding bar. As stated before, the label is the one that appears in the *Lexical Concept Panel* on *Column A*, therefore it is fundamental to change it immediately whenever adding a new lexical concept. The modification and changes in the label are automatically saved and updated through the *Core Panel*.

3.3.3.2. Edit definition

The definition of the lexical concept can be changed by typing in the corresponding bar. The modification and changes in the definition are automatically saved and updated through the *Core Panel*.

3.3.3.3. Add lexical entry: Is evoked by

Step 1. Search for a lexical concept in *Column A*, *Lexical Concepts Panel* through the *Search bar*. Select the lexical concept you need and it will be opened in *Column B*, *Core Panel*. In this section, look for the *Evoked by box*, press **+** and search for a specific lexical entry on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the results (lexical entries) available on the platform.

Step 2. Select the lexical entry you need, and it will be automatically added to the lexical concept. With the the lexical entry can be deleted.

Fig. 97 - Step 2. Add lexical entry: is evoked by

Step 3. At this point, this lexical concept should appear in the *Core Panel* of the lexical entry just linked, under the *evokes box*. In this example, in the *Core Panel* of the lexical entry *upsaseter*, we can see the lexical concept *Time*.

Fig. 98 - Step 3. Add lexical entry: is evoked by

3.3.3.4. Add sense: lexicalized senses

Step 1. Search for a lexical concept in *Column A, Lexical Concepts Panel* through the *Search bar*. Select the lexical concept you need and it will be opened in *Column B, Core Panel*. In this section, look for the *Lexicalized senses box*, press **+** and search for a specific

lexical entry on the *Search bar*. The bar will provide a scrolling window with all the results (lexical entry with its corresponding sense provided) available on the platform.

Step 2. Select the lexical entry you need - taking into account the sense provided - and it will be automatically added to the lexical concept. With the the lexical entry can be deleted.

Fig. 99 - Step 2. Add sense: lexicalized senses

Step 3. At this point, this lexical concept should appear in the sense *Core Panel* of the lexical entry just linked, under the *lexical concept box*. In this example, in the *Core Panel* of the lexical entry *upsed*, we can see the lexical concept *Time*.

Fig. 100 - Step 3. Add sense: lexicalized senses

3.3.4. Add child lexical concept

There are 2 ways of creating child lexical concepts:

3.3.4.1. Add child lexical concept - option window

Step 1. From *Column A, Lexical Concepts Panel*, click on a lexical concept, a window will be opened with different options. Select *Add Lexical Concept (child)*.

Fig. 101 - Step 1. Add child lexical concept - option window

Step 2. A green message will be shown to inform you that the child lexical concept is created, and it will be opened in the *Core Panel of Column B*.

Fig. 102 - Step 1. Add child lexical concept - option window

Step 3. Information can be managed as for lexical concept (detailed info see [3.3.2. Manage lexical concept](#))

3.3.4.2. Add child lexical concept - add icon

Step 1. From *Column A, Lexical Concepts Panel*, click on a lexical concept, which will be opened in the *Core Panel of Column B*.

Step 2. Click on **+** placed in the bottom gray bar of the Panel and select *Add Lexical Concept (child)*. The child will be created and opened in the *Core Panel* of *Column B*.

Fig. 103 - Step 1. Add child lexical concept - option window

Step 3. Information can be managed as for lexical concept (detailed info see [3.3.2. Manage lexical concept](#))

3.3.5. Search the lexical concept

3.3.5.1. General search

Fig. 104 - Lexical Concept General Search

The search bar enables the browsing of lexical concepts according to different parameters:

- **Starts:** you search all the lexical concepts that start with the string you typed.
- **Contains:** you search all the lexical concepts that contain the string you typed in the bar.

Keep in mind that lexical concepts are listed and written in capital letters, therefore the search should consider the upper-lower case.

4. Troubleshooting

This paragraph shows some of the most common recurring errors the user can encounter while using the interface. The table below reports the issues and guidelines to solve the problem.

Issues	Description	How to solve it
COPY OF EXISTING FILES WHILE UPLOADING INSCRIPTION	The platform does not recognize if there is a file with the same name of the file you are uploading somewhere in the platform (e.g. in a specific folder). The system doesn't recognise copies of existing files.	Before uploading, double-check if there is a file with the same name somewhere in the platform already
COPY-PASTE EXTERNAL LINKS	External links through copy-pasting are not recognized	Refresh the page and try to add the link again. If the error persists, try with another link. If the error persists, contact M. Mallia ¹²
DELETE LEXICAL ENTRY	I want to delete a lexical entry but it does not work	The service prevents me from deleting data that cannot be deleted. To delete a lexical entry, make sure you first deleted all the root elements in its tree first (e.g. sense, forms, etc)
DELETION OF TOKENS IN EMPTY FILES	Deleting a token does not automatically delete its related Attestation	If you delete a token, remember to also delete its related attestation
EPIGRAPHY SEARCH WITH OLD TEXT	For linking functionalities in the <i>Epigraphy Panel</i> , sometimes the search-form box appears with an old text search	Click outside the search-form box and re-click on the token you want to link an internal form element
GENERAL ERROR MESSAGE	Error message on the top right of the page while performing different kinds of actions (e.g. add lexical entry, add cognate, etc)	Try to refresh the page and perform the same action. If the error persists contact M. Mallia
LABEL LEXICAL ENTRY	The label of a lexical entry that I have just created, in the lexicon panel (column A), appears with its ID instead of its label	Refresh the page and in the lexicon panel will appear the correct label for the lexical entry you just created

¹² Michele Mallia, Research Associate (LaRI Group) at ILC A. Zampolli, CNR, Pisa. E-mail: michele.mallia@ilc.cnr.it

Issues	Description	How to solve it
LEXICAL CONCEPT CHILD	When I create a lexical concept child, the element appears as a sibling and not as a child.	Sometimes there is some incorrect behavior (especially over a certain level of deepness of the tree). Please, reload the lexical concept tree or refresh page.
LEXICAL CONCEPT DEFINITION	I want to use the Definition bar in the Core panel of Column B of a lexical concept.	Keep in mind that this section is not working, if you need to write something related to the definition of the lexical concept, please use the Note Panel in Column C. Problems will be solved as soon as possible by M. Mallia.
LEXICAL CONCEPT DELETION	If a lexical concept relation is added to a specific lexical entry, the only way to delete is from the Core Panel of the lexical entry, and not from the Core Panel of the lexical concept (same for senses)	The delete icon does not appear next to the lexical entry (evoked by box) in the Core Panel of a specific lexical concept. Make sure to delete it from the lexicon.
LEXICAL CONCEPT SEARCH	I have problems with the search of lexical concepts .	The search is uppercase-dependent. Remember that lexical concepts are in uppercase, while searching them you must use uppercase. (e.g. I want to search "Animals", the only way to have the right result is to use the letter "A" in uppercase).
LEXICAL CONCEPT VISUALIZATION IN TREE	It is possible that some lexical concept are not correctly visualized in the list of the Lexical Concept Panel even if they are correctly added to the platform.	If you can't see the lexical concept you need to search for it through the search bar, and the lexical concept will appear.
LEXICAL ENTRY IN LEXICON PANEL	The lexical entries in the <i>Lexicon Panel</i> disappeared.	Contact M. Mallia.
LEXICON TREE NODES	I can't see the children of a lexical / text node.	Wait 20 seconds, collapse, re-expand the node. In case, refresh the page.
OPEN IN A NEW PANEL AND BROWSER ICON	For linking functionalities, sometimes the open in a new panel icon, and the browser icon do not appear.	Refresh the page and check again, the icon should appear.
ORDER OF INSCRIPTIONS AND	The XML files in the Inscription Panels are not in	The available order of the inscriptions (and folders) does not reflect the classic numerical order such as 1, 2, 3,

Issues	Description	How to solve it
FOLDERS	alpha-numerical order.	... 100...200, etc. Yet, the order places at first all the files starting with 1, then starting with 2 etc. In this way, for example, ItAnt_Osca_12 .will be before ItAnt_Oscan_2.
PROBLEM WITH SEARCH	The search is not working. There is an uploading icon.	Refresh the page and try a search again.
UPDATE METADATA FOR INSCRIPTION	I want to update metadata but it does not work.	The metadata file MUST have the same name as the original text. Check if the title is the same. If not, change it. If the names do not correspond an error message will appear.
UPLOAD NEW INSCRIPTION	Error message while uploading a new text (inscription) from local.	The inscription text is already in the platform, or there is another text with the same title. Check if the text is already available or change the name.

5. User roles, permissions, and log-in

5.1. User roles

To access Epilexo, each user needs a specific account that allows them to use the editor platform. Accounts are created through the platform interface¹³. Each account has a specific role, preselected at the moment the account is created, and each role has specific and different permissions. Detailed information is provided in the next paragraphs.

There are 4 different roles for the Epilexo's users and accounts, each of them with a specific icon.

1. **Admin** : is allowed to perform any kind of action and use all the functionalities of Epilexo. He is also allowed to create accounts and manage them.
2. **Reviewer** : is allowed to perform the same action as the Admin except creating an account. He is allowed to change the status of a lexical entry to *Reviewed*.
3. **Editor** : is allowed to perform the same action as the Reviewer except changing the status of a lexical entry to reviewed, but he can change the status of the lexical entry to *Completed*.
4. **User** : is only allowed to visualize the content.

	Admin	Reviewer	Editor	User
Visualize content	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed
Create	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Not allowed
Manage/edit	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Not allowed
Delete	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Not allowed
Completed status	Allowed	Not allowed	Allowed	Not allowed
Reviewed Status	Allowed	Allowed	Not allowed	Not allowed
Accounts creation and management	Allowed	Not allowed	Not allowed	Not allowed

¹³ Another way to created and manage account is throught open source Keycloak software (<https://www.keycloak.org/>) . If further information are needed, please contact M. Mallia.

5.2. Account creations

Step 1. From the interface, click on the *user icon* on the top left of the platform, and it will open the *user manager page*.

Fig. 105 - Step 1. Account creation

Step 2. Click on the *add icon* in the *Create* blue box to add a new account. A new panel (*User details* panel) will be automatically opened on the right with all the detailed information needed in order to create a new account:

- **Username:** the user name of the account.
- **Email:** the email linked with that account.
- **Password:** a bar used to type a new and original password linked to the account.
- **Repeat password:** repetition of the chosen password.
- **Roles:** a scrolling window from which you can select the roles.
- **Enabled:** a toggle button that can be switched on or off if you want to enable or disable the account.

Add all this information to create an account, as shown below.

Fig. 106 - Step 2. Account creation

Step 3. Once all the information needed is added, you must enable the account with the toggle button, and then you can save the account by clicking on the *Register* box on the bottom right. The account will be automatically generated and the panel will change and provide the ID number of the account. The *delete user* red box will also appear on the bottom.

Fig. 107- Step 3. Account creation

Step 5. You can manage and edit the account created on the user manager page by simply clicking on the specific account username on the left column of the page.

5.3. User account management

5.4.1. Edit email

The email linked to the account can be changed by typing on the corresponding bar. Changes are saved by clicking on the blue *Update* button on the button right.

5.4.2. Edit password

The password linked to the account can be changed by typing a new password on the corresponding bar *Password*, and typing the same new password on the bar below *Repeat the password*. Changes are saved by clicking on the blue *Update* button on the button right.

5.4.3. Edit role

An account can have more than one role at once. In fact., roles can be added by selecting on the scrolling bar, and they can be deleted by clicking on the little X next to the role already assigned to the account. Changes are saved by clicking on the blue *Update* button on the button right.

5.4.4. Disable user

The account can be disabled by turning off the corresponding toggle button. Changes are saved by clicking on the blue *Update* button on the button right.

5.4.5. Delete user

The account can be deleted by clicking on the Delete User red box. A Wizard window will be shown.

5.4. Log-in and Log-out

5.4.1. Log-in

To log-in, open the online platform at the link: https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/epilexo_itant/lexicon. Write in the corresponding bars your username or email and password, and click on the Sign in button. The Editor platform will be opened.

Fig. 108- Log-in

5.4.2. Log-out

To log-out, or change your account, click on the username's button on the top right corner of the interface, and then click on "Logout", it will go back to the sign-in page.

Fig. 109 - Log-out

6. Icon keys

Icon	Name	Description
	add icon	allows to add new items (text, files, folders, lexical entry, language, form, sense, etymology, bibliography, morphological traits, cognates, representations, definition traits, and etylink)
	admin icon	icon that shows the admin role in the <i>user manager page</i>
	browser icon	opens a new tab of the LiLa page
	delete icon	allows to delete all kinds of items such as languages, attestations, forms, etc.
	edit icon	allows to edit a listed language in the Language Manager
	editor icon	icon that shows the editor role in the <i>user manager page</i>
	endpoint icon	enables the LiLa endpoint
	eye icon	shows a list of items: Lexical Entries related to a specific language in the Language Manager and Attestations of tokens in the Text Linker
	export icon	allows to export the entire lexicon as <code>.TXT</code>
	filter icon	enables filtered search in text and lexicon
	language icon	opens the Language Manager window
	label view icon	switches to label view in the Lexicon section
	note icon	shows notes on items (lexical entry, form, sense, etymology etc.)
	open in a new panel icon	It opens a new panel of a <i>Core Panel</i> of specific item (cognates or attestation). It opens a new tab for external resources from LiLa (from Etymons or Cognates). It opens a new tab of the Zotero Library.
	open in a new tab icon	opens a new tab of the original external reference's webpage (<i>Bibliography Panel</i>)
	question mark icon	shows examples for filtered searches in Column A or provides explanations of specific elements as morphological traits in the <i>Core Panel</i>

	reset icon	resets the search filters and parameters, and clear the formatting words in the <i>Note Panel</i>
	reviewer icon	icon that shows the reviewer role in the <i>user manager page</i>
	status icon	shows the status of the lexical entry
	synchronize icon	synchronize the external reference in Zotero Library
	user icon	opens the user page manager and it shows the name of the editor of a lexical entry or other elements
	user icon	icon that shows the user role in the <i>user manager page</i>

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